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The Impacts Of Anthropogenic Activities In The Niger Delta On Climate Change: Challenges And Prospects For Sustainable Development

Augustus N. Ebelegi¹

¹Department of Chemical Sciences,
Faculty of Science,
Niger Delta University, Bayelsa State, Nigeria
ebelegiaugustus@ndu.edu.ng

ABSTRACT

This review examines the impacts of anthropogenic activities in the Niger Delta on climate change, highlighting the challenges and prospects for sustainable development. The region, rich in oil and gas resources, faces severe environmental degradation due to activities such as oil exploration, gas flaring, deforestation, and industrial pollution. These activities contribute significantly to climate change by increasing greenhouse gas emissions, destroying carbon sinks, and altering weather patterns. Rising sea levels, coastal erosion, biodiversity loss, and declining agricultural productivity further threaten the region's ecological and socio-economic stability. The review identifies major challenges, including weak governance, over-reliance on oil, and environmental injustice affecting local communities. It also explores prospects for sustainable development through renewable energy, environmental restoration, economic diversification, and improved policy frameworks. The study synthesizes recent literature, offering policy recommendations and calling for further research into community-based climate adaptation and environmental governance. It concludes that addressing these issues through integrated and inclusive strategies is vital for the sustainable future of the Niger Delta.

Keywords: Climate Change, Anthropogenic Activities, Niger Delta, Environmental Degradation, Sustainable Development

1. INTRODUCTION

The Niger Delta, located in the southern region of Nigeria, is one of the most ecologically diverse and economically significant regions in the country. Spanning approximately 70,000 square kilometers, it is home to a complex network of rivers, mangroves, and wetlands that support a wide range of biodiversity. The region's natural resources, especially oil and gas, have played a pivotal role in Nigeria's economic development, with the Niger Delta being the primary source of the country's petroleum reserves. However, this wealth has come at a significant environmental cost. Over the years, however, the region has suffered extensive environmental degradation caused by oil exploration and exploitation activities, leading to considerable damage to its natural resources and ecosystems (Chijioke *et al.*, 2025). Climate change impacts, including rising sea levels, flooding, and altered rainfall patterns, are exacerbating the region's vulnerability. Consequently, the Niger Delta faces a dual challenge of addressing both human-induced environmental degradation and the global impacts of climate change (Onyekuru & Marchant, 2016; Okon *et al.*, 2021).

This review aims to synthesize existing research on the relationship between anthropogenic activities and climate change in the Niger Delta. By examining the environmental impact of human activities such as oil extraction, deforestation, and industrial pollution, the paper seeks to explore how these actions contribute to climate change in the region. It will also analyze the challenges posed by these activities to both the environment and local communities. Additionally, the review will evaluate the prospects for sustainable development in the Niger Delta, focusing on opportunities for mitigation, adaptation, and the promotion of environmentally sustainable practices. The paper will provide a comprehensive overview of the factors influencing the region's climate and the potential for long-term environmental stability.

This review is structured to address the key anthropogenic activities in the Niger Delta, their impacts on climate change, and the challenges the region faces in achieving sustainable development. The first section will focus on the primary human activities contributing to environmental degradation, such as oil extraction, deforestation, and industrial pollution. Following this, the review will examine the impacts of these activities on climate change, including changes in weather patterns, biodiversity loss, and rising sea levels. The third section will focus on the challenges to sustainable development, such as governance issues, the region's economic dependency on oil, and the socio-political factors hindering effective climate action. Finally, the review will explore the prospects for sustainable development in the Niger Delta, highlighting strategies such as renewable energy, environmental restoration, and policy reforms. This interdisciplinary approach combines environmental science, policy analysis, and socio-economic perspectives to provide a holistic view of the region's climate challenges and development prospects.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Anthropogenic Activities in the Niger Delta

Anthropogenic activities in the Niger Delta, including oil and gas extraction, deforestation, land use changes, industrialization, and inadequate waste management, have significantly contributed to environmental degradation. Oil extraction has caused widespread pollution, while deforestation and infrastructure development disrupt ecosystems, and poor waste management exacerbates health and environmental challenges in the region.

2.1.1 Oil and Gas Extraction

Oil and gas extraction is the primary anthropogenic activity in the Niger Delta and has significant environmental consequences. Studies show that oil spills, gas flaring, and other extraction activities result in soil contamination, water pollution, and air quality degradation (Ukhurebor *et al.*, 2021; Lusweti *et al.*, 2022; Ewim *et al.*, 2023; Bello & Nwaeke *et al.*, 2023). Oil spills, often caused by pipeline ruptures, are one of the major contributors to soil and water pollution, leading to the destruction of aquatic ecosystems and the contamination of drinking water sources. Gas flaring releases large amounts of carbon dioxide, a greenhouse gas that contributes to climate change by increasing atmospheric warming. Furthermore, these activities lead to the degradation of biodiversity and disrupt local communities' livelihoods (Ito & Ugbome, 2017; Oghenekohwiroro *et al.*, 2025).

2.1.2 Deforestation and Land Use Changes

Deforestation and land use changes in the Niger Delta have exacerbated environmental degradation and climate change. Urbanization, agriculture, and logging are major contributors to deforestation, leading to the loss of biodiversity and critical ecosystems such as mangroves and forests (Aransiola *et al.*, 2024). The loss of these ecosystems results in increased carbon emissions, as trees and vegetation play a vital role in carbon sequestration. Moreover, land use changes, including the expansion of agricultural activities, contribute to soil erosion and degradation, further diminishing the land's ability to support healthy ecosystems (Nasir Ahmad *et al.*, 2020). These activities not only harm biodiversity but also accelerate climate change by reducing the region's carbon sink capacity.

2.1.3 Industrialization and Infrastructure Development

The industrialization and rapid infrastructure development in the Niger Delta have resulted in increased environmental pollution, further exacerbating climate change. As industries expand, they often discharge untreated waste into rivers and streams, leading to water contamination and loss of aquatic life (Singh *et*

al., 2023). The growth of urban areas has also led to increased air pollution due to the emission of pollutants from factories, vehicles, and construction activities. Industrialization has contributed to soil contamination, particularly from the release of heavy metals and hazardous chemicals (Zhou *et al.*, 2024). These activities not only degrade the environment but also contribute to global climate change through the emission of greenhouse gases and the destruction of natural carbon sinks.

2.1.4 Waste Management

Improper waste management is a significant challenge in the Niger Delta, contributing to land and water pollution and exacerbating environmental degradation. Studies have shown that the Niger Delta region's poor waste disposal systems result in the accumulation of solid waste in both urban and rural areas (Opara *et al.*, 2025), which contaminates water sources and clogs drainage systems (Maiha & Yusuf, 2025). The improper disposal of plastic waste and industrial chemicals has led to soil and water contamination, affecting the health of local communities. This pollution also affects local biodiversity, as aquatic life is disrupted by chemical contaminants, leading to the decline in fish populations. The lack of effective waste management exacerbates climate change by contributing to the release of methane and other harmful gases from landfills, further increasing global warming (Lakhout, 2024).

2.2 Climate Change in the Niger Delta

Climate change in the Niger Delta brings about severe environmental, economic, and social challenges. The region's heavy reliance on oil production has accelerated environmental degradation, worsened climate change, and led to issues such as health risks and socioeconomic difficulties (Arausi *et al.*, 2025). Additionally, rising sea levels, flooding, and extreme weather events threaten the livelihoods of local communities.

2.2.1 Rising Sea Levels and Coastal Erosion

Rising sea levels, driven by global climate change and exacerbated by local anthropogenic activities, pose significant threats to the Niger Delta's coastal communities. Several studies highlight that the region, with its low-lying coastal areas, is particularly vulnerable to sea level rise (Danladi *et al.*, 2017; López-Dóriga & Jiménez 2020; Roy *et al.*, 2023). Oil exploration and deforestation have increased the susceptibility of coastal areas to erosion, which, in turn, accelerates habitat loss, reduces arable land, and disrupts local communities' livelihoods (Onyena & Sam, 2020). Coastal erosion is further intensified by rising sea levels, which inundate agricultural lands, destroy infrastructure, and cause saltwater intrusion into freshwater systems. This intrusion compromises water quality and agricultural productivity, affecting food security and the economy of the region. Studies indicate that the rate of coastal erosion in the Niger Delta has increased significantly, and without effective mitigation measures, it could lead to the displacement of thousands of residents (Chijioke *et al.*, 2025).

2.2.2 Weather and Climate Variability

The Niger Delta is experiencing notable shifts in its climate, with altered rainfall patterns, rising temperatures, and more frequent extreme weather events. Research shows that changes in rainfall patterns are resulting in longer dry spells and more intense, localized flooding during the rainy season affecting crop cycles, which are vital to the local economy (Fall *et al.*, 2020). Additionally, increased temperatures have led to the reduction of fish stocks, which are essential to the livelihoods of local communities that rely on fishing. Extreme weather events, such as storms and heavy rainfall, have also damaged infrastructure, further exacerbating the vulnerability of rural communities. As a result, local livelihoods, especially in agriculture and fisheries, are increasingly at risk, with long-term socio-economic consequences for the region (Ikehi, 2014).

2.2.3 Biodiversity Loss and Ecosystem Degradation

Anthropogenic activities, particularly oil extraction, deforestation, and industrialization, have led to significant biodiversity loss and ecosystem degradation in the Niger Delta. Studies show that mangrove forests, wetlands, and other crucial ecosystems are being destroyed by pollution from oil spills, gas flaring, and land use changes (Duke, 2016; Numbere, 2016; Onyena & Sam, 2020). These ecosystems serve as critical habitats for wildlife, including migratory birds, fish, and other species, and play essential

roles in regulating the local climate, water quality, and carbon sequestration. The degradation of these ecosystems reduces the region's capacity to adapt to climate change and weakens the natural defenses against environmental shocks such as floods and storms. The destruction of mangroves and wetlands, in particular, increases the risk of coastal erosion and reduces the region's biodiversity (Aransiola *et al.*, 2024). As these ecosystems continue to degrade, the services they provide, such as flood control, water filtration, and habitat for fish, are increasingly compromised, further threatening the sustainability of the Niger Delta's environment.

2.3 Challenges to Sustainable Development

Challenges to sustainable development in the Niger Delta stem from governance and political factors, economic dependence on oil, and environmental injustice. Weak governance structures hinder effective policy implementation, while reliance on oil perpetuates economic vulnerability. Environmental injustice further exacerbates disparities, as local communities face the brunt of pollution and neglect.

2.3.1 Governance and Political Factors

Governance issues and political instability remain major barriers to sustainable development in the Niger Delta. Studies show that corruption, weak political will, and ineffective governance have hindered the implementation of robust environmental policies in the region (Alibašić & Atkinson, 2023; Atta & Sharifi 2024; Handoyo 2024). The Niger Delta's oil wealth has led to political power struggles and inadequate enforcement of environmental laws, resulting in poor regulation of oil extraction and environmental degradation (Elisha & Gbaranbiri, 2024). Moreover, the lack of transparency and accountability in the management of natural resources has exacerbated the exploitation of the environment, leaving local communities vulnerable to pollution and environmental harm. The political instability in the region further complicates efforts to implement sustainable development policies, as it undermines the collaboration necessary between government, communities, and businesses to achieve environmental sustainability (Adebayo *et al.*, 2022).

2.3.2 Economic Dependence on Oil

The Niger Delta's heavy dependence on oil revenues has had profound implications for sustainable development in the region. The economic over-reliance on oil has led to a lack of diversification, making the region vulnerable to the fluctuations of global oil prices (Elwerfelli & Benhin, 2018). This dependence has hindered efforts to develop other sectors such as agriculture, tourism, and manufacturing, which are critical for long-term economic sustainability. Studies show that this lack of diversification contributes to poverty, as local communities are left without viable alternatives to oil-related livelihoods (Apata *et al.*, 2010). Furthermore, oil revenues have often been mismanaged, leading to inadequate investment in infrastructure, healthcare, education, and environmental restoration, which are crucial for fostering economic resilience and sustainable development in the Niger Delta (Felix & Precious, 2024; Nkem *et al.*, 2024).

2.3.3 Environmental Injustice

Environmental injustice in the Niger Delta is a key challenge to achieving sustainable development, as marginalized and indigenous communities bear the brunt of environmental degradation caused by anthropogenic activities. Research indicates that local communities, particularly those in oil-producing areas, suffer disproportionately from oil spills, gas flaring, and deforestation (Ewim *et al.*, 2023). These communities face health problems, loss of agricultural productivity, and displacement due to environmental harm. Additionally, the lack of compensation or remediation for the damage caused by oil extraction compounds the injustice, leaving communities in a cycle of poverty and vulnerability (Omokaro, 2024). The failure to address environmental justice issues has further exacerbated social inequality and undermined the region's potential for sustainable development by fostering resentment, social unrest, and conflicts between local populations and government or corporate entities (Willies, 2021).

3. METHODOLOGY (Approach to the Review)

3.1 Review Criteria and Selection of Studies

The studies selected for this review will be based on their relevance to the impacts of anthropogenic activities on climate change in the Niger Delta. Studies focuses on topics such as oil exploration, deforestation, industrialization, and their environmental consequences. Only studies published within the last 10 to 15 years were considered to ensure the inclusion of the most recent data and analysis. Additionally, preference was given to peer-reviewed academic journals, reports from reputable organizations, and official government publications that provide reliable and scientifically valid information. This selection criterion ensured that the review reflects current knowledge and relevant findings in the field of environmental science and climate change.

3.2 Data Collection and Synthesis

Data was collected from a variety of sources, including academic papers, government and NGO reports, and media articles, to provide a comprehensive view of the issues in the Niger Delta. These sources were accessed through academic databases, government publications, and reputable online platforms. The synthesis approach will involve categorizing the studies into key themes, such as anthropogenic activities (oil extraction, deforestation), climate impacts (rising sea levels, weather variability), and policy responses. A thematic synthesis summarizes the findings from different sources, identifying trends, patterns, and gaps in the literature, while highlighting both the challenges and prospects for sustainable development in the region.

4. ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Synthesis of Findings on Anthropogenic Impacts

The cumulative effects of anthropogenic activities in the Niger Delta significantly contribute to climate change. However, the oil and gas industry has generated a significant amount of toxic and hazardous waste, which has a detrimental effect on the environment (Shahbaz *et al.*, 2023), with associated pollution, including oil spills, gas flaring, and wastewater discharge, release greenhouse gases and toxic substances that degrade both air and water quality. These activities contribute to global warming and exacerbate regional climate change impacts (Oyerinde, 2018). Land-use changes, particularly deforestation and agriculture, have led to the loss of carbon sinks, resulting in increased carbon emissions and soil degradation (Wang, 2024). Furthermore, industrialization and improper waste disposal have intensified environmental degradation, with industries emitting pollutants into the atmosphere, while landfills generate methane, a potent greenhouse gas (Lakhout, 2024). These cumulative impacts accelerate climate change and environmental degradation in the Niger Delta.

4.2 Challenges in Addressing the Impacts of Anthropogenic Activities

Several challenges hinder effective action in addressing the environmental impacts of human activities in the Niger Delta. A key issue is the lack of effective regulation and enforcement of environmental laws, which allows industries to operate without adequate consideration for environmental sustainability (Okechukwu, 2024). Additionally, there is insufficient investment in alternative economic activities and sustainable livelihoods for local communities, leading to continued reliance on environmentally damaging oil extraction (Albert & Amaratunga, 2020). Political instability and corruption further exacerbate these issues, as governmental bodies often fail to enforce environmental policies or support community-led environmental initiatives (Handoyo *et al.*, 2024). These factors undermine efforts to mitigate climate change and promote long-term sustainable development.

4.3 Prospects for Sustainable Development

There are several promising prospects for sustainable development in the Niger Delta. Transitioning to renewable energy sources, such as solar and wind power, presents an opportunity to reduce reliance on fossil fuels and mitigate climate change impacts (Jaiswal *et al.*, 2022). Additionally, environmental restoration initiatives like reforestation, mangrove rehabilitation, and soil regeneration can help restore degraded ecosystems, enhance biodiversity, and improve carbon sequestration (Choudhary *et al.*, 2024). Economic diversification is also critical, with the promotion of agriculture, eco-tourism, and the

development of sustainable industries providing alternatives to oil dependency (Delechat *et al.*, 2024). Enforcing environmental standards and regulations is one of the most effective ways for governments to mitigate the negative impacts of multinational corporations (Lakhout, 2024). Finally, strengthening governance, policy frameworks, and encouraging community participation in environmental management are crucial for driving sustainable development in the region (Agrawal *et al.*, 2022).

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this review emphasizes that anthropogenic activities in the Niger Delta, such as oil extraction, deforestation, and industrialization, are major contributors to climate change. These activities have led to severe environmental degradation, including oil spills, pollution, and biodiversity loss, exacerbating the region's vulnerability to climate impacts like rising sea levels and extreme weather events. The challenges to sustainable development in the Niger Delta include poor governance, economic dependence on oil, and environmental injustice faced by local communities. Policy recommendations include strengthening environmental regulations, promoting renewable energy, diversifying the economy, and empowering communities in climate adaptation. Future research should focus on localized studies to assess the effectiveness of climate adaptation strategies and explore the role of community-based organizations in environmental governance. This will help develop policies that foster environmental sustainability and socio-economic resilience in the Niger Delta.

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